

Table 2. Susceptibility levels of rice pests to insecticides in some rice-growing countries in Asia.

Insect species	Country	Location	LD ₅₀ values (µg/individual)				
			Carbaryl	Carbofuran	Diazinon	Malathion	Monocrotophos
<i>Nilaparvata lugens</i>	India	Lab culture, Hyderabad	0.007	0.002	—	—	—
	Sri Lanka	Lab culture, CARI	—	—	—	—	0.008
	Thailand	Pathumthani	0.005	0.0007	—	0.07	0.004
		Phitsanulok	0.005	0.0004	—	0.09	0.003
	Indonesia	Sleman, Yogyakarta	0.005	0.0008	0.08	0.2	—
		Boyolali, Central Java	0.006	0.001	0.09	0.2	—
Japan	Tikugo, Hukuoka-ken	0.01	0.002	0.07	0.2	—	
<i>Nephotettix virescens</i>	India	Cuttack	—	—	0.01	—	—
<i>N. cincticeps</i>	Japan	Tikugo, Hukuoka-ken	—	—	0.6	15.2	—
<i>Cnaphalocrocis medinalis</i>	Sri Lanka	Alawwa	—	—	—	—	0.003
<i>Chilo suppressalis</i>	China	Changping, Beijing	0.3	0.07	—	0.3	0.3

difference in susceptibility level. LD₅₀ values from two collection sites in Thailand were comparable, indicating

the same susceptibility levels.

India and Japan gave susceptibility data for *N. virescens* and *N. cincticeps*.

The data for *C. medinalis* came from Sri Lanka, and those for *C. suppressalis* from China. □

Water management

Influence of planting method and irrigation practices on rice water requirement

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We studied the irrigation requirement of direct seeded and transplanted rice during 1986 dry season. Two methods of crop establishment were main plot treatments and 3 irrigation schedules (continuous shallow submergence with 5 ± 2 cm water, intermittent irrigation at 5-d intervals with 5 cm water except during flowering, and moderate stress) were subplot treatments. The test variety was IR36.

Soil texture varied from sandy loam to sandy clay loam and alluvium type Mahanadi River soil with pH 5.5. The water table was 40-60 cm deep during the crop duration.

Differences in grain yield due to irrigation schedules and method of planting and their interactions were significant (Table 1). The transplanted crop gave about 36% higher yield than the direct seeded crop. Continuous shallow submergence gave significantly

Table 1. Effect of moisture regime on yield of IR36 under direct seeded and transplanted conditions. Cuttack, India, 1986 dry season.

Moisture regime	Grain yield (t/ha)		
	Direct seeded	Transplanted	Mean
Continuous shallow submergence (5 ± 2 cm) (I ₁)	5.1	6.2	5.6
Intermittent irrigation at 5-d intervals (I ₂)	3.3	5.2	4.2
Moderate stress (I ₃)	3.0	4.1	3.6
Mean	3.7	5.2	
LSD to compare irrigation schedules (I)			6.0
LSD to compare method of planting (MP)			3.4
LSD to compare MP at the same level of (I)			5.8
LSD to compare I at the same level of MP			7.3
CV (%)			
MP			32.8
Irrigation schedule and interaction			22.5

higher yield than the two other water treatments. Reduced water application progressively reduced yield, with moderate stress giving the lowest yield.

Yield reduction due to less irrigation water in the intermittent flooding treatment was pronounced under direct seeded conditions. There was not much scope for further yield reduction under moderate stress. On the other hand, yield differences were significant between the two lower water regimes under transplanted conditions.

Irrigation requirements are presented in Table 2. The irrigation water required to maintain continuous shallow

Table 2. Water used by different irrigation treatments. Cuttack, India, 1986 dry season.

Water regime	Water requirement (mm)	
	Direct seeded crop	Transplanted crop
Continuous submergence	2250	2000
Intermittent irrigation	1100	950
Moderate stress	800	750

submergence was more than two times that required for intermittent irrigation. □